

A MULTIFUNCTIONAL MICROPOROUS POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITE WITH GRAPHENE NANOPATELETS

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1 General Introduction

Polymeric materials combined with a small amount of nanoparticles offer new possibilities in the synthesizing of multifunctional materials. Polymers are an ideal matrix to greatly benefit from the addition of nanofillers because they are currently limited in their applications due to their low mechanical properties and low thermal and electrical conductivities. However, polymers have significant advantages such as their ease of processing, low density and cost effectiveness.

A microporous multifunctional polymer (e.g. foam) would be even more attractive for aerospace applications if a balance between structural properties and multifunctionality can be achieved. Recent discoveries in carbon-based nanostructures make them an ideal multifunctional nanofiller because of their excellent properties. Different carbon nanofillers have been utilized in polymer foams to improve mechanical properties such as carbon nanofibers and carbon black in polyurethane foams [1,4] and carbon nanotubes in polyurethane and poly(methyl methacrylate) foams [2-3]. Nanoclays have also been utilized in various flexible and rigid polymer foams [5-6]. These various nanofillers have been found to improve the mechanical strength and physical properties of the foam. In addition using electrically conductive carbon fillers has resulted in foams that have a lower resistivity and show promise as electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding devices [7-11]. The potential applications for a lightweight electrically conductive polymeric material extend to use as electrostatic discharge protection materials, actuators and photoconductors [10].

Graphene is one such carbon filler that has the potential to greatly improve the performance of

polymer foams. Not only does this material exhibit excellent mechanical properties and electrical conductivity but it also has high thermal conductivity, which expands the use of a multifunctional composite to a thermal heat sink. In addition graphene can be made at cost-effective prices compared to other carbon-based nanofillers. Expanded graphite has successfully been used in polyurethane composites alone and with carbon black to increase conductivities but also demonstrated significantly degraded mechanical properties believed to be due to particle agglomerations [12-13]. This research focuses on the reduction of agglomeration by better understanding the relationship between graphene nanoplatelets and a polymer matrix thereby creating a multifunctional low density material with good mechanical performance and low electrical resistivity.

1.1 Polyurethane foam

Polyurethane foam utilized as the matrix in a microporous polymer, which has a well-studied chemistry, can be synthesized easily by combining two reactive components with a blowing agent that allows the polymer to cure and foam simultaneously. The structure-processing-property relationships for polyurethane foams are well known and the constituents are commercially available making it an ideal matrix for investigation.

1.2 Graphene Nanoplatelets

The nanofiller utilized in this work is a graphene nanoplatelet. Graphene is a single layer of graphite and consists of a hexagonal arrangement of sp²-hybridized carbon atoms. This structure is responsible for the excellent in plane thermal, electrical, mechanical and barrier properties of graphene. Currently the challenge with graphene is its high cost of synthesis that limits its applications.

A novel process developed at Michigan State University can produce a 3-15 nm thick stack of graphene nanoplatelets (GnP) with lateral dimensions in the micrometer range at low cost. The GnP still maintain a high tensile modulus of ~1000 GPa, high electrical, 10^7 S/m, and thermal, 3000 W/m-K, conductivities in a more robust form consisting of a few layers of graphene stacked together [14]. The thickness can be kept in the nanometer range with increasing lateral dimensions giving it a variable aspect ratio.

2 Experimental Procedures

2.1 Materials

Polyurethane forms by a condensation polymerization between isocyanate and hydroxyl groups. The isocyanate, supplied by Huntsman, is a polymeric diphenylmethane diisocyanate (Rubinate M, NCO value: 31.1%). The hydroxyl groups are a polyol mixture of polyether diols with differing amounts of hydroxyl content (Jeffol G30-650, $M_n \sim 260$ and Jeffol FX-231, $M_n \sim 700$) both also supplied by Huntsman and mixed with ethylene glycol according to the formulation shown in Table 1. Air Products kindly supplied the blowing and trimerization catalyst (Dabco BL-11 and Dabco TMR-3) as well as the polysiloxane surfactant (Dabco DC193). Distilled water is used as the blowing agent. A rigid, 0.19 g/cm^3 , closed cell polyurethane/polyisocyanurate (PUR/PIR) foam is generated using these components according to the formulation shown in Table 2. The isocyanate reacts with the water to produce carbon dioxide during polymerization to generate the foam. The varying sizes and thickness of GnP were supplied by XG Sciences and were initially heat treated at 450°C for 2 hours prior to being utilized.

2.2 Procedure

Two different procedures were employed using these materials. One procedure generates polyurethane foam and the other produces a monolithic polymer when the blowing agent is removed from the formulation. In both procedures the polyols and ethylene glycol are combined and mixed for 2 hours. Then the two catalysts, surfactant and blowing agent are added and mixed for 1 hour to generate the foam. For the solid polyurethane

sample only the trimerization catalyst is added at the ratio listed in Table 2 and stirred for 1 hour. The polymeric diphenylmethane diisocyanate (pMDI) is poured into a separate container. GnP is added to the polyol mixture and the polymeric diphenylmethane diisocyanate (pMDI) reactant separately. Each component is then high-speed shear mixed at 1600 rpm for 1 minute and 2400 rpm for 2 minutes. After shear mixing the GnP is ultrasonicated in the individual reactants with a probe at ~100 W until well dispersed. The dispersion of the GnP in the polyol blend is evaluated with a reflectance optical microscope prior to the mixing of the two reactants; an example of which is shown in Fig. 2. Once the polyol blend and pMDI mixture are combined they are mechanically stirred for 45 seconds before being poured into a mold and allowed to cure overnight.

Some samples contain pMDI treated GnP. The pMDI treated GnP were synthesized by first heating the GnP to approximately 150°C before adding pMDI. This solution was allowed to react with the GnP for either 1 hour or overnight at 150°C . The GnP is then repeatedly washed with acetone to remove excess pMDI before the GnP is dried.

2.3 Testing Methods

Nanocomposite foam is a three phase system consisting of the polymer matrix, nanofiller and gas. The goal of removing the blowing agent from the polyurethane samples was to gain insight regarding how the GnP interacts with the polymer matrix, so it became necessary to decrease the vast volume expansion that occurs during foaming to get an accurate representation. Thermal properties were measured with differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and were compared with images of the dispersion. These dispersion images were made on a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) and the samples were coated with gold prior to being cut with a focused ion beam (FIB). FIB uses a focused beam of gallium to cut through materials to get an accurate representation of the dispersion. The functional groups on the pMDI treated GnP were characterized using x-ray photoelectron microscopy (XPS). The foam samples had the same thermal and imaging tests performed as well as mechanical and electrical resistivity testing. The mechanical testing

was done on United Testing Systems mechanical load frame. Four test samples were cut from each foam. Each sample was 2.54 cm x 5.08 cm² and compressed according to the procedure outlined in ASTM standard D1621-04a. The electrical resistivity measurements were done using a two-point probe on three test samples measuring 40 mm x 10 mm x 3 mm.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Results

Several types of GnP have been embedded into the polymer foam matrix. GnP-25 and GnP-5 designate GnP with an average diameter of 25 μm and 5 μm , respectively, and a surface area of around 120 m²/g. GnP-C-750 is a high surface area material with diameters of less than 1 μm and surface area of 750 m²/g. "Standard" designates a sample made without GnP.

3.2 Discussion

There is a definite correlation between the electrical and mechanical properties. In general it appears that samples with good electrical contact do not have good mechanical properties and in some cases even degrade it. Ideally GnP would improve both the polymers mechanical and electrical properties. Electrical behavior relies on the ability of the GnP to form a conductive pathway (percolated network), which suggests the GnP needs to have at least point-to-point to contact to allow electron transfer or be close enough to facilitate electron tunneling. Agglomerations would not necessarily degrade electrical conductivity but for the sake of mechanical properties it is to be avoided as much as possible because they considerably degrade the mechanical performance of the polymer. Even with the assistance of ultrasonication to disperse GnP into the reactants, agglomerations were still observed and reflect the negative correlation between mechanical and electrical properties in Fig. 5 and 6. The smaller GnP-5 platelets produce the largest increase in compressive modulus and strength. The larger GnP-25 platelets are less effective at increasing the mechanical properties but blends of the two sizes show a synergistic effect. A decrease in electrical resistivity is achieved and is found to depend heavily on the aspect ratio of the GnP. The percolation threshold for GnP-25 is at 4 weight percent, whereas

with a smaller GnP size a larger concentration is required to achieve percolation. The blends of the two sizes again show a synergistic effect but still resulted in agglomerations and thereby mechanical degradation.

In order to reduce agglomeration the chemical interaction between GnP and the polymer matrix was investigated. This was achieved using the lab formulation mentioned previously by simply removing the blowing agent and blowing catalyst. The polysiloxane surfactant was also removed from this synthesis, as its purpose is to create a uniform blowing morphology and could potentially influence how the GnP interacts with the polymer matrix. Thermal degradation behavior was observed with TGA but little change was found between the samples with varying concentrations. There were four peaks observed on the degradation profile. The first peak is around the decomposition temperature of pMDI, which shows that not all the isocyanate reacts to form urethane. The peaks at 300°C have to do with the decomposition of urethane [15]. Higher decomposition temperatures at around 400°C are due to the isocyanurate trimer and urea decomposing [16]. Anything above 450°C is the decomposition of GnP.

Observations of the glass transition temperature were far more insightful in determining the effects that GnP has on the molecular structure of the polymer. The changes in the glass transition temperature (T_g) were measured with the DSC and interesting phenomenon was observed between the varying concentrations in the solid polymer samples shown in Table 4.

The glass transition temperature of a standard non-foam sample without blowing agent was found to be 118.1°C. This is very close to the samples with GnP and suggests that the GnP interacts slightly with the polymer matrix and may even interfere with the amorphous regions ability to become more flexible and rubber-like upon heating. There is, however, some reaction with the pMDI treated GnP that allows the pMDI or some derivative to adhere to its surface and further interact with the polymer matrix thus allowing the glass transition to shift to lower temperatures. To determine what chemical groups were on the surface of the pre-treated GnP, XPS was

employed. There are oxygen groups, mostly hydroxyl groups, on the edges of 'as received' GnP as confirmed with XPS. Since hydroxyl groups can react with isocyanate it became necessary to investigate which groups formed on the edges of the GnP after reacting with pMDI. The nitrogen 1s spectra for the GnP after reacting with pMDI for over 12 hours is shown in Fig. 8.

For pMDI reacted GnP three peaks were found to appear in the nitrogen spectra. Since baked GnP contains no nitrogen groups it was assumed that the nitrogen groups result solely from the reaction of the pMDI with the GnP. By comparing these nitrogen spectra to the nitrogen spectra of a urethane sample it was confirmed that the central peak at 400 eV is from the urethane group. As urethane reacts and forms during the polymerization process other polymers such as polyurea and biuret form. These are probably responsible for the higher binding energy peak. The lower energy peak is likely unreacted pMDI that is instead adsorbed on the GnP surface.

Since urethane groups form on the surface of the GnP it is not surprising that they interact more with the polymer matrix on a molecular level as seen from the changes in the glass transition temperature. The change in the glass transition temperature with pMDI treated GnP-5 is larger than that with the pMDI treated GnP-25 even though the glass transition temperature for the non-treated GnP between the two sizes was similar. With GnP-5 there are more edges thereby edge groups to react with, but the concentration of the total nitrogen groups on the GnP-5 was less compared to the GnP-25. However, the majority of nitrogen groups on the GnP-5 are urethane, which may just have a stronger interaction with the molecular network.

Since the goal of this research was to create a conductive network without degrading the mechanical properties, the percolation threshold must be exceeded. Particles with a larger aspect ratio achieve this at a lower concentration [7], but have a tendency to agglomerate. It was found that all sizes of GnP easily agglomerated and restacked even in samples without blowing agent. So pre-treating with pMDI was done in hopes that the GnP could be dispersed without agglomeration.

Fig. 9 shows that the GnP still tends to stack together even with pMDI pretreatment, which is not necessarily surprising since the urethane only forms on the edges of the GnP and not the basal plane where the van-der-Waal forces would be strongest. Functionalizing the basal plane is not a good strategy since it is responsible for the excellent mechanical, electrical and thermal properties of the graphene.

This same sort of behavior was observed in the foam samples. Two types of phenomenon happen during foaming: expansion causes the distance between the GnP to increase, but at the same time GnP is being compressed together radially forming a 3D cell structure (Fig. 10). The addition of GnP affects the foaming behavior, possibly due to the increase in viscosity, which is observed in the change in the exothermic reaction during gas evolution (Fig.13).

The expansion during foaming of the polymer did not create enough of a shear stress to force the GnP to orient in desired ways regardless of the size of the GnP as can be seen in Fig. 12. The GnP-C-750 is the smallest diameter of GnP and is ideal for going into the thin struts (< 4 μm thick), which they successfully do, but from Fig. 12 it can be seen that the GnP-C-750 still lies perpendicular to the expansion direction.

Pre-treating the GnP with pMDI prior to adding to the foam seems to offer little improvement over agglomeration. The pMDI treated GnP used in the foam was reacted for less time (1 hour) and resulted in more of the functional groups on the GnP being urethane as shown in Table 5. This functionalization did not reduce agglomeration, however, as seen from the FESEM images, but there was marked improvement in the mechanical properties which may be attributed to the edge groups of the GnP bonding better with the polymer matrix. The bonding, however, is not strong enough to force the GnP to reorient along the flow direction during expansion.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

This research has shown that the addition of GnP to a polyurethane matrix has the potential to improve the mechanical properties and electrical conductivity

of a rigid, 0.19 g/cm³ PUR/PIR foam. The biggest challenge is reducing the GnP agglomeration. A perfect conductive network would be one in which the percolation threshold is achieved at the lowest concentration of GnP and would maintain mechanical performance which has yet to be achieved. This research, though, has confirmed the importance of aspect ratio in the formation of a conductive network. Larger sized GnP is able to achieve lower resistivity at lower concentrations. However, smaller sizes of GnP do a better job of getting into thin struts but still do not orient along the flow direction.

Information gleaned from this work regarding the interaction of GnP with a polymer foam will be used in investigating a nanocomposite foam using polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) matrix. PDMS is a common polymer used in aerospace applications due to its good mechanical flexibility at low temperatures. Functionalization of the GnP will be investigated since this polyurethane research has shown that there needs to be a strong interaction between the polymer and the GnP for it to orient in the flow direction during expansion. Since good electrical contact is still desired in these PDMS samples differing sizes of GnP will be investigated including hybrids of different sizes and functionalities of GnP. The overall goal of this research is to create PDMS nanocomposite foams of optimal performances with tailorable properties for specific aerospace applications.

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Fig. 1. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of a graphene nanoplatelet on filter paper.

Table 1 Ratio for mixing the differing polyol components.

Polyol blend component	Concentration (parts)
Jeffol FX-231	70
Jeffol G30-650	15
Ethylene Glycol	15

Table 2 Formulation for making the rigid 12 lb/ft³ PUR/PIR foam.

Component	Concentration (pphp)
Polyol blend	100
Dabco DC193	0.8
Dabco BL-11	0.05
Dabco TMR-3	0.6
Distilled water	0.4
Polymeric MDI	158

Fig. 2. Reflectance optical microscope image of 6 wt% GnP-25 in polyol blend that contains no blowing agent.

Fig. 3. Compressive strength of rigid PUR/PIR foam with varying concentrations and sizes of GnP.

Fig. 4. Elastic properties of rigid PUR/PIR foam with varying amounts and sizes of GnP.

Fig. 5. Electrical resistivity of PUR/PIR foam at varying concentrations and sizes of GnP.

Fig. 6. Mechanical Properties of a rigid 12 lb/ft³ PUR/PIR foam from a commercial system by Stepan.

Fig. 7. Electrical resistivity of a rigid 12 lb/ft³ PUR/PIR foam made from a commercial system by Stepan.

Fig. 8. PUR/PIR rigid with 5 wt% pMDI treated GnP-25 no blowing agent.

Table 3 Glass transition temperature determined from the DSC profile of rigid PUR/PIR with GnP and without blowing agent

Non-foam samples	T _g (°C)
Standard	118.1
5 wt% GnP-25	119.6
5 wt% pMDI treated GnP-25	117.3
8 wt% GnP-5	119.9
8 wt% pMDI treated GnP-5	112.7

Fig. 9. Nitrogen 1s spectra of pMDI treated GnP-25 reacted for over 12 hrs.

Table 4 Concentration for different nitrogen groups on GnP pretreated with pMDI.

N 1s spectra peak	Concentration GnP-5 (atomic %)	Concentration GnP-25 (atomic %)
401.3	0.56	0.62
400	2.52	2.90
399	0.38	1.63

Fig. 10. SEM image of a focused ion beam (FIB) cut of a strut of a PUR/PIR sample containing no blowing agent with 5 wt% GnP-25.

Fig. 11. FESEM image of PUR/PIR rigid sample with 5 wt% pMDI treated GnP-25 and no blowing agent.

Fig. 12. FESEM image of PUR/PIR 12 lb/ft³ rigid foam with 8 wt% GnP-C-750.

Fig. 13 Temperature profile of a rigid 12 lb/ft³ PUR/PIR foam sample with and without 5 wt% GnP-25.

Fig. 14. FESEM image of PUR/PIR rigid 12 lb/ft³ foam with 8 wt% GnP-C-750 strut prepared by FIB.

Fig. 15. FESEM image of PUR/PIR rigid 12 lb/ft³ foam with 8 wt% GnP-5 strut prepared by FIB.

Table 5 Nitrogen spectra of pMDI treated GnP reacted for 1 hr.

N 1s spectra peak (eV)	Concentration GnP-5 (atomic %)	Concentration GnP-25 (atomic %)
401.3	1.37	0.30
400	4.26	2.71
399	0.53	0.25

Fig. 17. FESEM image of an agglomerate in PUR/PIR 12 lb/ft³ rigid sample with 8 wt% pMDI treated GnP-25. Surface was prepared with a FIB.

Fig. 16. FESEM image of an agglomerate in PUR/PIR 12 lb/ft³ rigid sample with 5 wt% pMDI treated GnP-25. Surface was prepared with a FIB.